

A Study of Risks Factors Affecting Online Shopping in Faisalabad

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Abstract— This is the era of technology and companies are becoming globalized. Now companies are facing tougher competition. This is their need to be innovative if they want to be in the competition. Technologies not only provide benefits to users but also have negativity. Shopping through the internet is very common now days. It not only made shopping tasks easy but also has many risks. The study explores the risks of online shopping. Population was selected from Faisalabad city and two hundred and fifty respondents were selected as sample. Different data analyses techniques were used to find out the Frequency, percentages, Chi –square Degree of freedom, P-value, Gamma, mean and standard deviation. Research has found that consumers are worry about security from internet shopping and the main risk of online shopping was the loss of privacy and to provide personal information to online sellers.

Keywords— *online shopping, easy way of shopping, risk of security, risk of loss of privavty.*

I. INTRODUCTION

E-commerce helps to buy and sell the products on internet. It also facilitates many countries to pay their different kinds of bills online and consumers do not need to go out to pay bills and shop the products. The beginning of internet shopping has been started few years ago and now it is becoming very important part of our lives as it provides us more convenience and ease and the products we need are now just one click away. Online shopping is the demand of current time as it is the way to shop in convenient way and also companies are earning more profit while selling the products on internet. This is the reason for which companies are making websites and spread their business on internet as well. “ The significance for retailers to having a web site is that a web site is informational and transactional in nature (Murphy, 1998)” [5]. Websites should be design in a way that provide full information about the product which is offered on the website for sale and the contents to buy the product online should be easy to understand and use. Online business increases its sale in holidays and specific occasions because people want to spend their time with family or friends and want the products at their doorsteps.

Consumers can adopt internet as a shopping medium only when they are aware about new technology and also they accept and using of technology. According to Davis (1998)

conducted research under Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) which is used to conduct study about the workers how they accept and use technology at their work.

According to the research of. Shim et al. (2001) and Vijayasathy (2004) consumers must be familiar with computer and internet [11]. How to connect to internet and what are the search engines to help the customs [9]. Consumers also must have information about different online shopping stores that are established to sell their products online. When consumers aware about the internet usage than internet can positively or negatively influence on his/her online shopping decisions.

Singh and Sirdeshmukh (2002) stated that trust is very important phenomenon and it is a psychological state which is based on positive expectations on others [10]. And in online business of selling, it is very important to get the trust of customers and it is the most important factor which influences the success or failure of e-business. Consumers are afraid of different kinds of internet frauds like credit card steeling, fake website, low quality, or difference between the product order and product delivered. It is very important step for retailers to make trustable relationship with their consumers that will not only retain the customer but also strengthen the brand. According to the press article (Vintone 2001) it has expressed that trust is the main factor that increase or decrease the online business [12]. Consumers are afraid of different kinds of internet frauds like credit card steeling, fake website, low quality, or difference between the product order and product delivered. It is very important step for retailers to make trustable relationship with their consumers that will not only retain the customer but also strengthen the brand.

A. Rationales of study

The study will be beneficial for online companies to perform specific activities to get customers trust for online store. The research will be beneficial for offline consumers who avoid online shopping because of risk factors.

B. Objectives

To identify the risks of online purchasing.

To analyze the strength of risk factor for the failure of online shopping.

C. Hypothesis

Higher risks in online shopping leads to reduce online purchases.

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D. Conceptual Framework

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Risk

When consumers feel satisfaction while purchasing online it means the risk factor is less (Monuwe et al. 2004) [4]. Trust is the main factor that influence the customer's online shopping. If consumers feel lack of trust to the online store than they will avoid purchasing from that source (Lee and Turban, 2001) [3]. The main reason that influences customers to avoid online shopping is customer's lack of trust in online store. When customers do not want to provide their personal information to the online shopping store, it means they do not have trust on online seller. When customers feel risk while visiting online shopping store, they definitely avoid providing their personal and economical information to the e-store. Customers want full assurance of security and privacy from the seller before purchasing online. Perceived risk increases psychological costs when feelings of discomfort occur in an individual (Stone and Gronhaug, 1993). Perceived risks have two main focuses. The first one related to delivery issues that consumers may face while purchasing and second is privacy and security (Johnson, 2006) [2]. There are many risks that consumers may face while making online shopping. Shopping from the online store is a new way for consumers and they want to experience this with some purchases. Perception of convenience in online stores and its informative sources has positive effect on purchasing decision (Sorce et al. 2005) [14]. When risks are higher than purchasing from internet is low. Consumers avoid buying products from that online store that do not provide any guarantee or replacement of products in case of damage or defect. Consumers do not show positive response to the online store that do not build trustable relations with customers and do not assure them about privacy and security.

Consumers are worry about security from internet shopping (Wong and Sculli, 2005) [13]. It will leads to avoid online shopping. When consumer's perceived risk is lower, then their purchasing intention will be higher (Park, 2002) [7]. When consumers purchase high cost product or those products which are sensitive in nature, they need more security from the online sellers. These securities are providing accurate information about product, confidentiality of product and buyer's information, security of same size and color that has been displayed on the web page. To buy clothes from internet is most risky item to be purchased as size, color and fitting

counts a lot to the customers who buy such products online (Park, 2004) [6]. Online shopping cannot provide access to the customers to try the product. Size may vary from company to company. Besides that, quality of a product cannot be physically checked by the consumers. Internet is a rich source of getting product related information in depth (Park, 2004) [6]. It will help to reduce the level of risk while purchasing online as risk is expected to be more in online shopping than offline shopping. Perceived risk in online shopping can be reduced if read the information of the product before final purchase. Internet marketers should create trustable relationship with customers that will not only increase sale of company but also make the customers loyal. During research it is come to know that consumers are afraid of fake websites located on internet and they did many frauds with customers because they were charged all amount of product before the delivery and never deliver the products. Now many online shopping stores in Pakistan facilitating their customers to pay the price of product at the time of delivery. Some online stores also facilitating to replace the product within specified time period in case of any defect or complain. These activities help the customers to get more trust on web store. When customers do trust on online store they will start purchasing to that store and with good online shopping experience, the number of online purchases increase.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Nature of the study

The study was designed to analyze the strength of online shopping's risks factors. How risks affected online purchasing decision. One hypothesis was proposed and tested by using statistical tools. Study has also identified the relationship of hypothesis and calculated level of significance of the hypothesis.

B. Study setting

Research gathered primary data from Pakistani nationals live in Faisalabad city. Both male and female were selected as respondent. Different college and universities students, Government organizations and females stay at home were selected as respondents. Secondary data was gathered from research journals and research articles.

C. Time horizon

A time horizon is also known as a planning horizon. It is a fixed period of time in the future to which certain investigation processes expected to complete. The research study was based to resolve the current problem. The cross sectional study mode was selected to investigate the research problem. It is a kind of observational study includes the analysis of data collected from population at one particular point and time.

D. Data collection instrument

Questionnaire is used to collect data. The questionnaire consists of five point Likert scale. The scale started from 1 and ended on 5. 1 means strongly disagreed, 2 disagreed, 3 neither agreed nor disagreed, 4 agreed and 5 mean strongly agreed. Total two hundred questionnaires were finally received from respondents. Language was simple English that is easily

understandable to the target customers. All related groups of people were selected and it was preferred to select both online shoppers and non-innovative buyers. Before data collection various social websites have been visited and it was noticed that many new web stores has established to sell their products. These online stores do not mention any traditional store address. They have only their websites and cell numbers to contact. These online selling websites were also thoroughly visited and got many respondents of Faisalabad city. Their experience and opinions were also very helpful. This exercise was very helpful to compare the different online stores. Famous and well known brand's online stores were visited online and these stores have many outlets and seemed less risky. Their customers were also considered for information and got their responses. This practice helped a lot to compare responses of different web stores. Different traditional markets has also visited and collected the data from the people who used offline stores for shopping purpose.

E. Research Population

The research population is defined as the large number of people who have some common characteristics or habits. This population was selected to resolve the research queries. All Faisalabad's internet users were selected as population. Total two hundred and fifty responses were gathered from respondents.

F. Sampling method and sampling frame

Sampling is a process of selecting a number of individuals for study in a way that sample represent the large group on

individuals from which they were selected. Sample is a smaller but representative set of population that participates in research to determine results. Purposive sampling technique was used as it is best technique used to investigate specific purpose. Sample size was three hundred respondents and from them two hundred and fifty respondents was fully participated to provide their responses and remaining fifty questionnaires were not treated as the part of research because of no feed back by respondents. One hundred and fifty questionnaires were distributed to universities and colleges in Faisalabad, sixty questionnaire were distributed to the business people, sixty questionnaires were distributed to private business sectors and remaining thirty questionnaire were spread to different homes for the responses of women stay at home. Both male and females were selected to fill the questionnaire and 165 male and 85 females were filled the questionnaire. The percentage of participated male respondents was (66.0%) and female respondents were (34.0%). The respondents of universities and colleges were participated (50%), business men (20%), private organizations (20%) and house women were participated (10%) to the responses.

G. Measures and methods

Study data was analyzed with the help of univariate analysis and bivariate analysis. Chi square, degree of freedom, gamma, p value, frequencies, percentages, mean and standered deviation were applied to measure the level of significance among dependent and independent variables. whole calculations were completed with the help of statistical software of social sciences names SPSS software.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Univriate analysis

TABLE 22: DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESPONDENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR OPINION ABOUT RISKS

Risks	Strongly disagree		Disagree		Neither agreed nor disagreed		Agree		Strongly agree	
	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
a: I consult somebody before internet shopping.	44	17.6	74	29.6	40	16.0	28	11.2	64	25.6
b: The quality of products on internet is cheaper.	20	8.0	80	32.0	102	40.8	34	13.6	14	5.6
c: The product's information on net is not accurate.	20	8.0	94	37.6	90	36.0	28	11.2	18	7.2
d: I avoid online shopping because of difference between product's display and product which is delivered.	22	8.8	52	20.8	96	38.4	56	22.4	24	9.6
e: The product's delivery	28	11.2	52	20.8	124	49.6	20	8.0	26	10.4

process is very slow.										
f: I feel risk while giving my debit/credit card number.	17	6.8	28	11.2	141	56.4	20	8.0	44	17.6
g: I avoid online shopping because online products have no guarantee/warranty.	16	6.4	42	16.8	70	28.0	104	41.6	18	7.2
h: I feel risk to buy from the company which is not well reputed.	20	8.0	36	14.4	46	18.4	112	44.8	36	14.4
i: I feel risk of loss of privacy.	10	4.0	33	13.2	85	34.0	70	28.0	52	20.8
j: Advance payment of product is a hurdle.	43	17.2	101	40.4	26	10.4	46	18.4	34	13.6

Majority of respondents were agreed (29.6%) and consult somebody before internet shopping as they feel online markets risky. Disagreed respondents were (11.2%) percents. These respondents do not consult anybody before internet shopping. As these respondents has experience of online purchase and decide to purchase all alone. But majority of online respondents consult somebody before internet purchase. When respondents were asked about the quality of internet are cheaper, respondents who were neither agreed nor disagreed had (40.8%), and respondents who were disagreed contributed (32%). These respondents had good online shopping experience and they found that the online purchased product's have good quality. Quality also depends on the brand or store from where customers are purchasing. Well known brands do not compromise with their quality and provide good quality in their products whether purchase online or offline. Agreed respondents were (13.6%). These respondents had bad experience of online shopping respondents who were neither agreed nor disagreed contributed (40.0%). Research concluded that the quality of products on internet is not cheaper. Opinions of respondents about the statement that "I avoid online shopping because there is difference between product display and product delivered" respondents who said 'agreed' were (22.4%), these respondents think that online shopping has difference in product displays or delivers in size, color, material or shape etc. Respondents who said 'disagreed' were (20.8%), respondents who said 'neither agreed nor disagreed' were (38.4%). Research has concluded majority of respondents avoid online shopping because they found difference between product that has ordered and the delivered product. Majority of respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed about 'the product's delivery process is very slow' these natural respondents were (49.6%). After that majority of respondents were disagreed (20.8%). These respondents experienced in time delivery whatever the brand they have ordered on internet. Agreed respondents were (8%) only. Conclusion by the majority of responses was that in online product's delivery process is not very slow. Respondents provided their opinions about they feel risk while providing their debit/credit card number to the online store. Majority were neither agreed nor disagreed (56.4%), respondents who

were strongly agreed got (17.6%). These respondents do not want to give their debit/credit card number while shopping online as there are many fake websites are working on internet and they are just fraud. Strongly disagreed respondents were (6.8%) percents. Conclusions of the research is that majority of online shoppers feel risk while giving their debit/credit card number.

Respondents were requested to provide their opinions about the guarantee/warranty of the online products. Majority of respondents were agreed (41.6) about that online products do not have guarantee/warranty. Some online stores provide guarantee to their customers but majority of customers do not trust on internet stores. Disagreed respondents were (16.8%). Respondents who were neither agreed nor disagreed contributed (28.0%). It is concluded by responses that respondents avoid online shopping because online products have no guarantee/warranty. When it was asked to the respondents 'they feel risk for purchasing products from unknown online store' most of them were agreed as they were (44.8%) these respondents were very conscious about risks and they avoid online shopping from the unknown or new online store. Disagreed respondents were (14.4%), respondents who were neither agreed nor disagreed contributed (18.4%). Conclusion by the research is that consumers feel risk to buy from the company which is not well reputed. Majority of respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed (34.0%) when asked 'online shopping has risk of loss of privacy' after that majority of respondents were agreed and they were (28%). These respondents feel risk to provide their debit/credit card numbers and they avoid providing their home address to online store. Disagreed respondents were (13.2%). These respondents feel no hesitation and risk to share their personal information to others. It is concluded by research that majority of respondents feel risk of loss of privacy. Respondents provided their opinions about advance payment that most of the online stores charge before the product's delivery. Customers have to pay the amount of product in advance. Respondents who were majority were disagreed and they were (40.4%). These respondents do not consider advance payment as a hurdle as they have to pay the amount later or earlier. Agreed respondents were (18.4%) and these respondents want to pay cash after the delivery of

product. They want to check and match the specification of product at the time of delivery. Conclusions by the majority of responses is that advance payment of product is not a hurdle.

TABLE 23: MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION AND RANK ORDER OF THE RESPONDENTS' OPINION ABOUT RISKS

Risks	Mean	Std. Dev.	Rank
I feel risk of loss of privacy.	3.48	1.084	1
I feel risk while giving my debit/credit card number.	3.18	1.067	2
I avoid online shopping because of difference between product's display and product which is delivered.	3.03	1.082	3
I consult somebody before internet shopping.	2.98	1.464	4
The product's delivery process is very slow.	2.86	1.066	5
I feel risk to buy from the company which is not well reputed.	2.82	1.209	6
The quality of products on internet is cheaper.	2.77	.975	7
I avoid online shopping because online products have no guarantee/warranty.	2.77	1.039	8
The product's information on net is not accurate.	2.72	1.011	9
Advance payment of product is a hurdle.	2.71	1.320	10

Table 23 represents the respondents' opinion about risks. I feel risks of loss of privacy (mean=3.48) was ranked as 1st on the basis of risks. I feel risk while giving my debit/credit card number (mean = 3.18), I avoid online shopping because of difference between product's display and product which is delivered (mean=2.98), The product's delivery process is very slow (mean=2.86), I feel risk to buy from the company which is not well reputed (mean=2.82), The quality of

products on internet is cheaper (mean=2.82), The quality of products on internet is cheaper (mean=2.77), I avoid online shopping because online products have no guarantee/warranty (mean= 2.77), The product's information on net is not accurate (mean = 2.72) were ranked 2nd to 9th, respectively. Advance payment of product is a hurdle (mean = 2.71) fell in low category and ranked as 10th.

TABLE 24: DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESPONDENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR OPINION ABOUT ONLINE SHOPPING

Online shopping	Strongly disagree		Disagree		Neither agreed nor disagreed		Agree		Strongly agree	
	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
a: Are you satisfied with online shopping?	29	11.6	83	33.2	32	12.8	76	30.4	30	12.0
b: I prefer online shopping rather than traditional shopping.	30	12.0	90	36.0	78	31.2	34	13.6	18	7.2
c: Online shopping is an	17	6.8	57	22.8	112	44.8	36	14.4	28	11.2

easiest way to shop.										
d: I feel more comfort while shopping online.	33	13.2	30	12.0	137	54.8	30	12.0	20	8.0
e: Internet facilitates traditional companies to open their virtual stores.	10	4.0	110	44.0	52	20.8	56	22.4	22	8.8
f: Customer relations are weaker with internet sellers.	44	17.6	72	21.6	44	17.6	54	28.8	36	14.4
g: Online shopping is a great way to check variety of products and nobody is there to force you to shop quickly.	48	19.2	86	34.4	68	27.2	32	12.8	16	6.4
h: Online shopping is mostly kind of impulse buying.	17	6.8	32	12.8	139	55.6	38	15.2	24	9.6
i: Online shopping has a positive impact on me.	17	6.8	52	20.8	118	47.2	29	11.4	34	13.6
j: I suggest others for online shopping.	21	8.4	66	26.4	78	31.2	39	15.6	46	18.4

When respondents were asked about their satisfaction with online shopping, highest percentages respondents were disagreed (33.2%). These respondents were not satisfied with online shopping. Respondents who were agreed and satisfied with online shopping were (30.4%). Respondents who were neither agreed nor disagreed were (12.8%). Strongly disagreed respondents were (11.6%) and finally strongly agreed respondents were (12.0%). Conclusion of research is that majority of respondents are dissatisfied with online shopping. Responses were found by respondents about the statement that 'I prefer online shopping rather than traditional shopping' respondents who said 'disagreed' were (36%), respondents. These respondents prefer online shopping as most of them they enjoy online shopping process and found it convenient way of shopping for them. Respondents who said 'neither agreed nor disagreed' were (31.2%). As majority of responses were against online shopping, research has concluded that majority of respondents do not prefer online shopping rather than traditional shopping. Majority of respondents are neither agreed nor disagreed with online shopping provide more convenience to shop the desired products as they were total (44.8%) respondents. Respondents who were disagreed contributed (22.8%) These respondents like traditional way of shopping and consider offline shopping has easier process. Respondents who are agreed were (14.4%) respondents. Conclusion of research is that online shopping is not an easiest way to shop. Majority of respondents are neither agreed nor disagreed to feel more comfort while shopping online. These respondents were (54.8%). Respondents who were strongly

disagreed contributed total (13.2%). Strongly agreed respondents have were (8.0%) percents. It is concluded that majority of respondents feel more comfort and convenient while doing traditional shopping rather than online shopping. Respondents were strongly agreed with the statement that "internet facilitates traditional companies to open their virtual stores. These agreed respondents contributed (44%). Strongly disagreed respondents were (4.0%) percents. When got responses about customer's relationships are weaker with internet seller, majority of respondents were agreed as they got (28.8%) percents. These respondents consider online seller and buyer have weak relationship as no face to face communication is possible in online dealing. (21.6%) respondents were disagreed as there are not different ways to connect with online sellers like phone calls and emails. respondents who were neither agreed nor disagreed were (17.6%). Conclusion of the study is that Customer relations are not weaker with internet sellers in online markets. Respondents provided their opinions about 'online shopping is a great way to check the variety of products' respondents who said 'strongly agreed' were (34.4%). These respondents found online market as a big shopping place to screen, analyze, and evaluate the product and there is no restriction to buy the product. Respondents who said 'strongly disagreed' were (19.2%). These respondents were more comfortable to check the variety of products in traditional markets and they were unfamiliar to find the variety of product in online markets. Research has concluded that online shopping is a great way to check variety of products and nobody is there to force you to

shop quickly. When asked to the respondents about online shopping is kind of impulse buying, Majority of respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed and they were (55.6%) respondents. Agreed respondents were (15.2%), disagreed respondents were (12.8%), strongly agreed respondents were (9.6%), and strongly disagreed respondents were (6.8%). Conclusion of the study is that online shopping is mostly kind of impulse buying. Responses about the statement “online shopping has a positive impact” majority of respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed (47.2%), disagreed respondents were (20.8%), strongly disagreed respondents were (6.8%), agreed respondents were (11.4%), and strongly agreed respondents were (13.6%). Majority of respondents were not in favor of online shopping as they like traditional way of

buying products. Reasons varied from respondents to respondents as some of them feel convenient to do traditional shopping, some respondents feel online shopping a lengthy process to get the product. Consumers also face warrantee/guarantee issues etc. conclusion of the study is that online shopping has negative impact on majority of respondents. When respondents were asked about their suggestion on online shopping to others, majority of respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed (31.2%), disagreed respondents were (26.4%), agreed respondents were (15.6%), (8.4%) respondents were strongly disagreed and (18.4%) respondents were highly recommended others to start online shopping. But majority of respondents were against online shopping and they do not suggest others to shop online.

TABLE 25: MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION AND RANK ORDER OF THE RESPONDENTS’ OPINION ABOUT ONLINE SHOPPING

Online shopping	Mean	Std. Dev.	Rank
I suggest others for online shopping.	3.31	1.184	1
Online shopping has a positive impact on me.	3.23	1.045	2
Online shopping is mostly kind of impulse buying.	3.08	.966	3
Online shopping is an easiest way to shop.	3.00	1.047	4
Are you satisfied with online shopping?	2.98	1.259	5
I feel more comfort while shopping online.	2.90	1.040	6
Internet facilitates traditional companies to open their virtual stores.	2.88	1.080	7
Customer relations are weaker with internet sellers.	2.86	1.331	8
I prefer online shopping rather than traditional shopping.	2.68	1.080	9
Online shopping is a great way to check variety of products and nobody is there to force you to shop quickly.	2.53	1.131	10

Table 25 represents the respondents’ opinion about online shopping. I suggest others for online shopping (mean=3.31) was ranked as 1st on the basis of online shopping. Online shopping has a positive impact on me (mean = 3.23), Online shopping is mostly kind of impulse buying (mean=3.08), Online shopping is an easiest way to shop (mean=3.00), satisfaction with online shopping (mean=2.98), I feel more comfort while shopping online (mean=2.90), Internet

facilitates traditional companies to open their virtual stores (mean=2.88), Customer relations are weaker with internet sellers (mean= 2.86), I prefer online shopping rather than traditional shopping (mean = 2.68) were ranked 2nd to 9th, respectively. Online shopping is a great way to check variety of products and nobody is there to force you to shop quickly (mean = 2.53) fell in low category and ranked as 10th.

B. Bi-Variate analysis

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis 1: Higher risks in online shopping leads to reduce online purchases

TABLE 1: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RISKS AND ONLINE SHOPPING

Risks	Online shopping			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Low	33	18	5	56
	58.9%	32.1%	8.9%	100.0%
Medium	30	86	18	134
	22.4%	64.2%	13.4%	100.0%
High	5	16	39	60
	8.3%	26.7%	65.0%	100.0%
Total	68	120	62	250
	27.2%	48.0%	24.8%	100.0%

Chi-square = 145.28 d.f. = 4 P-value = .000** Gamma = .880
 ** = Highly significant

.Bi-variate analysis calculated association between risks and online shopping. Respondents who have low level of risk contributed in online shopping at low level (58.9%), medium level (32.1%), and high level (8.9%). Respondents who have medium level risk performed online shopping activity at low level (22.4%), medium level (64.2%), and high level (13.4%). Respondents have high level of risk involved in online shopping at low level (8.3%), medium level (26.7%), and high level (65.0 %.)

Chi-square value (1457.28) shows a highly significant association between risks and online shopping. Gamma value shows a strong positive relationship between the variables. It means risks have positive impact on online shopping. So the hypothesis “Higher risks in online shopping leads to reduce online purchases” is accepted. Results of the study match with (Park, 2004) when consumer's perceived risk is lower, then their purchasing intention will be higher [6]. If consumers feel lack of trust to the online store than they will avoid purchasing from that source (Lee and Turban, 2001) [3].

V. CONCLUSION

A. Conclusions and discussion about results

The research has found the risks of online shopping and the main risk of online shopping was the loss of privacy and to provide personal information to online sellers is consider risky. Providing debit/credit card numbers to the online sellers are also risky in case of advance payment of product. According to (Johnson, 2006) perceived risks have two main focuses. The first one related to delivery issues that consumers may face while purchasing and second is privacy and security [2]. According to (Wong and Sculli, 2005) consumers are worry about security from internet shopping [13]. According to (Chen and Chang, 2003) delivery of product by the online store is one of the main factors of online shopping as consumer does not need to physically reach and collect the product from the store. Internet shopping requires least effort, and allows the consumers to get all products' related information (Monsuwe et al. 2004) [1]-[4]. Perception of convenience in online stores and its informative sources has positive effect on purchasing decision (Sorce et al. 2005). Factors that are cause of failure of online shopping are lack of tangibility of product. According to Rajamma and Ganesh, (2007) consumer is very conscious about tangibility of products [8]. Online shopping is not convenient mode of

shopping and do not provide fun and enjoyment. Online shopping does not save time and money. Only fewer numbers of articles are available to purchase. Presentation of product is not good on internet stores and no face-to-face contact with seller. Finally online shopping does not provide privacy and security to the online consumers. According to the (Johnson, 2006) perceived risks have two main focuses [2]. The first one related to delivery issues that consumers may face while purchasing and second is privacy and security. The above all literature is aligned with the results of the study of online shopping.

B. Limitation of the study

The study was limited to only one city of Pakistan named Faisalabad. Research could be better if multiple cities selected for responses

C. Recommendations

Research study provides detailed information about risks that restrict the consumers to shop online. Online stores should make trustable relationship to the consumers to make them repetitive customers. Online stores should advertise their online as it is found by the research that 72 percents of people use internet daily but only 12.4 percent of people buy the

products from virtual stores. study will help the consumers to resolve their confusion about virtual stores.

D. Scope for future

On the basis of results of the study, it is recommended to increase to scope of online shopping in future. The affect of

customer relationship management for online stores need to be explore.

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